

ISic1264

I.Sicily inscription 1264

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 243

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Στάτειος
2. Εὐτύχης
3. ἔζησε ἀμέ[μ]
4. πτωσ ἔτη · ις
5. μῆνες γ
6. ἡμέρας · ζ

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004 and IG XIV

Translation (en)

Stateios Eutyches, lived blamelessly for 16 years, 3 months, 7 days.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492871

EDCS 39101633

PHI 140753

PHI 316306

Bibliography

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